

Part 6 Biomechanics in endodontics (Article Series), investigating the real effect of the post, tension resistant to prevent restoration dislodgement, a novel approach via numerical model, Stupid models for interpreting living organs

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Abstract

Endodontically treated teeth could end with severe tooth structure loss. This could be ended with what seems to be a non-restorable tooth that necessitates enforcement. 2 ways of enforcement are available, either via bonding or intracanal post placement. In this paper, we want to analyze the real role of the intracanal post.

Keywords: Dentine, Biomechanics, dental stiffness, teeth, stiffness of teeth, jaw weakeners.

Introduction

Endodontically treated teeth in many cases ended with severely destroyed crown or just root, where sometimes necessitate gingiva manipulation to lengthen the clinical remaining structure and provide a stump for better mechanical retention. The main function of the post is to resist the dislodgement of the filling out of its position. This issue had not been clearly represented in the scientific literature. (1)

This is associated with fulcruming, where the tooth is compressed in the side away from the force application site.

Figure 1 A simple representation of how the post stabilizes the filling in the case of lateral force is exerted.

The lateral force will make the post in a state of being pulled out of its place. Nevertheless, the dislodgment is not pure tension in nature, but with some sort of bending. In this paper, we want to represent this concept mechanically via a numerical model.

Methods

We used our current model in this series to manifest the true mechanical performance and different aspects of using soft and stiff posts in the endodontically treated tooth.

Figure 2 The base of the model is fixed, and the blue surface is the region where the load has been applied

The studied models have no adhesion between the crown and the root, where a contact boundary condition has been assumed

- Model with stiff post
- Model with soft post

In this paper, we want to compare the model of soft post to the model of stiff post, which is of high clinical application importance. The model of perfect contact had been studied in other papers. The used model is the same model used in the other papers in this series.

Results and discussions

The results are in favor of the use of metallic posts with a higher modulus of elasticity, and they will pave the way to characterize this issue numerically. The bonding with the tooth will be deteriorated day by day, and ultimately it will fail unless it had sound backup of mechanical support from the remaining tooth structure itself. The remaining tooth structure ensures that the transmission of the stresses is in the best way.

Figure 3 The concept of gap opening is apparent with its essential end by the pressure contact on the other side.

The gap opening at one side is associated with pressurized contact at the other side, where this will end by loss of the materials by wear and tear or even secondary carious incidence, resulting in even more deleterious stress on the whole region.

Figure 4 The figure on the left indicates that the loss of contact due to any cause will end in accelerated damage, and the failure will ensue more dramatically.

The first issue to be dealt with is the contact pressure. Although contact pressure here is not significant as in the case of titanium dental implants, it remains a significant issue to be investigated.

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Figure 5 Contact pressure with the metallic post on the left side is much less than that occurring on the right side, where the soft plastic post had been used.

Figure 6 The assumed gap opening will indirectly indicate the pressure introduced at this region. A stiffer post is highly advantageous in the preservation of the adhesion of the crown to the remaining tooth structure.

Figure 7 Anyhow, the metallic post gives better results. As with all of the other models, the strain energy density will be transferred more deeply and better. We suspect that the crack initiation and propagation will be from the most coronal region, although this issue needs more investigation on standardized fresh samples where orthotropicity is present in the best way.

Figure 8 Post pull-out results depend upon 3 factors (post-cement interface, cement dentine interface, and the cement itself). So that the failure could be adhesion or cohesive due to the defect in the cement itself. The metallic post will provide better stress transfer.

The cement with the metallic post condition is much better than the cement with the fiber post.

Figure 9 One of the advantages of the numerical simulations is that we can evaluate multiple aspects in a single shot. The concept of a fulcrum is very important to consider in the evaluation of the posted endodontically treated teeth.

In many instances, this question will be faced when we start to make a conclusion about biomechanics for living tissues, to which these studies are sound?

The answer is simply yes. (2) (3) (4)

Figure 10 The pattern of deformation of the plastic post due to the difference in the Poisson's ratio and modulus of elasticity is causing all of these features to occur.

Figure 11 Post cement interface in the case of the metallic post is anticipated to be more durable and longer-lasting.

Figure 12 The shear strain at the post cement interface is more uniform with the metallic post and more intense and severe with the plastic post, indicating that the metallic post bond is more durable.

Figure 13 Inspection of the displacement, tension, and compression in the well-welded model also reveals the same results. The strain at the interface between the crown and the root is tension at a region and compression at the opposite side. This fulcrum is of paramount importance to be understood. In the case of teeth without furrle the presence of a post is mandatory to provide the necessary mechanical support that provides the longevity for the prosthesis.

We should always remember that: (All models are numbers-driven, which should be approached parametrically)

In conclusion, all the engineering criteria clearly show the concept of levering and dual compression and tension at opposite locations. The stiffer material will produce better responses that respect dentine's limited capacity to tolerate protracted stresses from daily activities.

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Mohammed Zahid Saadoon BDS– FKHCMS (Maxillofacial Surgery). During 2014-2024, he was involved in many researches in biomechanics and biomechatronics. He developed many theories in maxillofacial traumatology, craniofacial growth, and dental implantology. He developed a unique dental implant system. He has a special interest in mechanical engineering applications in the medical and dental specialties as well as in forensic medicine. He is now working as a maxillofacial surgeon in Ashty teaching hospital, the largest secondary referral center in Soran discrete at Kurdistan region / Iraq.